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IMPACT OF CARDIOVASCULAR RISK FACTORS AND INFLAMMATORY STATUS ON URINARY 8-OHdG IN ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Background: The urinary concentrations of 8-OHdG reflect the oxidation status of hypertensive subjects and it can be used for monitoring oxidative stress changes. However, the influence of cardiovascular risk factors and inflammation on the urinary levels of this marker in hypertension has never evaluated. The purpose of this study was to analyze the impact of cardiovascular risk factors, and established inflammatory markers on 8-OHdG in essential hypertension.</p> <p>Methods: We studied 149 asymptomatic hypertensive patients (61 ± 14 years). A routine physical examination, laboratory analyses and echo-Doppler study were performed. Urinary 8-OHdG and plasma TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2 and IL-6 were determined.</p> <p>Results: 8-OHdG/creatinine levels were higher in hypertrophic patients (p=0.022) and correlated with left ventricular mass index (p<0.01). When 8-OHdG/creatinine was compared according to obesity and diabetes in our hypertensive subjects, no significant differences were found. 8-OHdG/creatinine was increased in hypertensive smokers (p=0.032) and women (p=0.006). Furthermore, 8-OHdG/creatinine correlated</p>

with TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2 ($p < 0.0001$) and with IL-6 ($p < 0.05$). A multivariate linear regression analysis showed that gender, smoking and TNF-alpha were independent factors of 8-OHdG/creatinine.

Conclusions: Urinary 8-OHdG was increased in hypertensive patients with hypertrophy even under medical treatment. The presence of other cardiovascular risk factors on top of hypertension do not alter the concentrations of this oxidative stress marker, only smoking increasing its levels. TNF-alpha is an independent factor of 8-OHdG. These data suggest that this urinary marker gives specific additional information, further than blood pressure control alone, when evaluating hypertensive patients.

ANSWER TO REVIEWER #2 COMMENT

First of all, we want to thank Reviewer #2 for his helpful comment.

With respect to last sentence in the Discussion Section “*These data suggest that this urinary marker gives specific additional information further than blood pressure control alone, and its calculation may contribute to optimize medical treatment”*”, we agree with Reviewer #2. Thus, we have deleted this sentence in the Discussion Section and Abstract:

“These data suggest that this urinary marker gives specific additional information, further than blood pressure control alone, when evaluating hypertensive patients”. (Discussion Section, page 14, line 12 and Abstract, page 3, line 23)

Once again, we would like to thank Reviewer #2 for his pertinent comments and suggestions that have helped improve the manuscript.

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IMPACT OF CARDIOVASCULAR RISK FACTORS AND INFLAMMATORY STATUS ON URINARY 8-OHdG IN ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION

Running head: Urinary 8-OHdG in essential hypertension

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ABSTRACT

Background: The urinary concentrations of 8-OHdG reflect the oxidation status of hypertensive subjects and it can be used for monitoring oxidative stress changes. However, the influence of cardiovascular risk factors and inflammation on the urinary levels of this marker in hypertension has never evaluated. The purpose of this study was to analyze the impact of cardiovascular risk factors, and established inflammatory markers on 8-OHdG in essential hypertension.

Methods: We studied 149 asymptomatic hypertensive patients (61 ± 14 years). A routine physical examination, laboratory analyses and echo-Doppler study were performed. Urinary 8-OHdG and plasma TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2 and IL-6 were determined.

Results: 8-OHdG/creatinine levels were higher in hypertrophic patients ($p=0.022$) and correlated with left ventricular mass index ($p<0.01$). When 8-OHdG/creatinine was compared according to obesity and diabetes in our hypertensive subjects, no significant differences were found. 8-OHdG/creatinine was increased in hypertensive smokers ($p=0.032$) and women ($p=0.006$). Furthermore, 8-OHdG/creatinine correlated with TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2 ($p<0.0001$) and with IL-6 ($p<0.05$). A multivariate linear regression analysis showed that gender, smoking and TNF-alpha were independent factors of 8-OHdG/creatinine.

Conclusions: Urinary 8-OHdG was increased in hypertensive patients with hypertrophy even under medical treatment. The presence of other cardiovascular risk factors on top of hypertension do not alters the concentrations of this oxidative stress marker, only smoking increasing its levels. TNF-alpha is an independent factor of 8-OHdG. **These data suggest that this urinary marker gives specific additional information, further than blood pressure control alone, when evaluating hypertensive patients.**

INTRODUCTION

The excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) has been referred to as oxidative stress, and in the cardiovascular system it is implicated in many pathophysiological conditions such as hypercholesterolemia, diabetes, hypertension (HT), and cardiac hypertrophic remodeling¹⁻⁴. Vascular oxidative stress has been demonstrated in spontaneous and experimental models of HT⁵⁻⁷. But, unlike the findings in animal models, the association between oxidative stress and HT in humans is less consistent, and results vary depending on the marker of oxidative damage being investigated⁸. In addition, there is evidence that oxidative stress is related to inflammation and endothelial activation in patients with essential HT^{9, 10}.

Furthermore, cardiac adaptation in response to intrinsic or external stress involves a complex process of chamber remodeling and myocyte molecular modifications. A fundamental response to increased biomechanical stress is cardiomyocyte hypertrophy. ROS stimulate myocardial growth, matrix remodeling, and cellular dysfunction, activating a broad variety of hypertrophy signaling kinases and transcription factors¹¹. In cultured cardiomyocytes, hypertrophy induced by angiotensin II, endothelin 1, norepinephrine, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF-alpha), or pulsatile mechanical stretch has been shown to involve intracellular ROS production and to be inhibited by antioxidants¹².

There are several untoward events that occur as a consequence of oxidative stress, including modification of proteins, lipid oxidation, and oxidative modifications of DNA. 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) is a product of oxidative DNA damage and a biomarker of the total systemic oxidative stress *in vivo*¹³. In a previous study, the content of damage-based 8-OHdG in nuclear and mitochondrial deoxyribonucleoproteins of hypertensive subjects was significantly higher than that of

the normotensive controls³. In addition, urinary 8-OHdG reflects the oxidation status of hypertensive subjects and this marker could be used for monitoring oxidative stress changes in these patients¹⁴. It has been published that the impact of the different cardiovascular risk factors, such as low levels of high-density lipoprotein, triglycerides, abdominal obesity or elevated fasting glucose on 8-OHdG genomic and mitochondrial, is minimal in patients with essential HT¹⁵. In a later study, hypertension was the strongest determinant of oxidative stress in a high risk cardiovascular population¹⁶. However, to the best of our knowledge, the influence of cardiovascular risk factors and left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) on the levels of urinary 8-OHdG in patients with essential HT has never been evaluated. Similarly, the relationship of the levels of this urinary marker and inflammation status has yet to be addressed.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to analyze the impact of LVH, cardiovascular risk factors, and inflammation (TNF-alpha, its soluble receptors and IL-6) on urinary 8-OHdG levels in patients with essential hypertension.

METHODS

Patients

The study was performed on 149 Caucasian hypertensive consecutive out-patients (age 61 ± 14 years, 82 male). Patients analyzed in this study met these inclusion criteria: a previous diagnosis of hypertension, as defined by the Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure¹⁷. Furthermore, exclusion criteria were secondary HT, heart failure, left ventricular ejection fraction <50 , ischemic (medical history, echo-Doppler, troponin T assay) or dilated cardiomyopathy, atrial fibrillation, more than mild valvular disease,

acute and chronic liver or renal diseases, immunological diseases, HIV, alcoholism and drug addiction and any other life-threatening disease.

All patients underwent a routine physical examination, electrocardiogram, echo-Doppler study and laboratory analyses. Physicians using a standardized protocol measured systolic and diastolic blood pressure in the left arm of seated subjects between 08:00 and 11:00 AM, following the recommendations of The American Heart Association¹⁷.

Patients were on stable medical therapy for at least 2 months before study enrollment with 59% angiotensin II receptor antagonist, 50% diuretics, 37% angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, 31% statins, 23% calcium-channel blockers, and 15% β -blockers. No patients were treated with vitamin A, E or C. Body mass index was calculated as the weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared, and obesity was defined as body mass index >30 kg/m². Metabolic syndrome was defined according to JNC 7 Treatment Guidelines¹⁷. Glomerular filtration rate was calculated using the modified diet in renal disease equation¹⁸. The procedure was approved by the appropriate institutional review boards or ethics review committees of each study center, and the study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of good clinical practice and with ethical standards for human experimentation established by the Declaration of Helsinki. Every patient signed a written informed consent for their inclusion in the study.

Laboratory determinations

Venus blood was taken by venipuncture with the subjects in sitting position between 08:00 and 11:00 AM. Subjects also provided a urine sample, the first urine of

the day. After centrifugation at 1300 rpm and 4°C for 10 min, urine and plasma samples were separated and stored in cryotubes at -80°C until assayed and only thawed once. Before the analysis, the urine samples were centrifuged twice at 13,200 rpm at 4°C for 30 min to avoid possible 8-OHdG measurement interferences produced by the precipitation of salt in urine.

Urinary levels of 8-OHdG and plasma concentrations of TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1 and sTNF-R2 were determined in a single laboratory by specific commercial sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (New 8-OHdG Check, Jaica ELISA kit, Japan; Strakine human TNF-alpha ELISA, Strathmann Biotec, Germany; Hbt human sTNF-R1 ELISA test kit, The Netherlands; Hbt human sTNF-R2 ELISA test kit, The Netherlands; Strakine human IL-6 ELISA, Strathmann Biotec, Germany). The tests were quantified at 450 nm in a dual wavelength microplate reader (Sunrise, TECAN, Austria) using Magellan software (version 2.5 TECAN, Austria). The TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and 8-OHdG tests have limits of detection of 1.3 pg/mL, 25 pg/mL, 25 pg/mL, 0.3 pg/mL and 0.5 ng/mL, respectively. Our CV intra-assay and inter-assay were for 8-OHdG (4.9% and 5.3%), TNF-alpha (7.4% and 8.9%), sTNF-R1 (6.5% and 9.1%), sTNF-R2 (4.7% and 7.6%) and IL-6 (6.1% and 8.3%), respectively.

Echo-Doppler study

The study was performed using standard hospital echocardiographic systems equipped with 2.5-4 MHz transducers. The echocardiographic examinations were performed using the standard apical and parasternal long axis views. Doppler echocardiogram images were stored on videotape and analyses of recordings were all performed in a central laboratory. M-Mode and two-dimensional images, Doppler

spectrum and color Doppler were analyzed off-line. For each patient, four consecutive beats were measured and averaged for each Doppler variable.

To obtain left ventricular ejection fraction, the area-length method was used¹⁹. Mitral flow propagation velocity (Vp) was determined using the previously described method²⁰. E/A ratio and deceleration time (DT) were also calculated. Left ventricular mass was measured following the Devereux method²¹ and in our study, LVH was defined as $>46.7 \text{ g/m}^{2.7}$ in women and $>49.2 \text{ g/m}^{2.7}$ in men²². Intra-observer variability was consecutively evaluated in series of 40 patients. Variability was expressed as the absolute difference divided by the mean value of echocardiographic measurements, for left ventricular mass variability being $8.4 \pm 6\%$.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation and categorical variables as a number of patients or percentage. Results for each variable were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov Smirnov method. TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and 8-OHdG concentrations exhibit a non-normal distribution and were presented as the median and interquartile range and log transformed (and proved to be normalized) before parametric correlation analysis. They were compared using the Student's t-Test and comparisons between more than two groups were performed by 2-tailed ANOVA. Correlations were performed using Pearson's coefficient.

Furthermore, multivariate linear regression analysis was performed using log transformed 8-OHdG/creatinine as dependent variable and included age, gender, known HT duration, blood pressure, total cholesterol, body mass index, diabetes mellitus, current smoking, LVH, Vp, TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2 and IL-6 as independent

variables. The discrimination of the best model was based on the principle of least mean square and higher R-square.

A *p* value <0.05 was considered significant for all measures. All statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS statistical software package (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL).

RESULTS

As shown in Table 1, the mean age of the 149 patients with essential hypertension was 61 ± 14 years, with 82 males (55%) and 67 females. Study subjects were previously diagnosed with significant comorbidities including obesity (43%) diabetes mellitus (16%) and metabolic syndrome (37%). In addition, in this group of hypertensive patients we found 23 current smokers (15%) and 69 subjects with LVH (46%).

Urinary levels of this marker were higher in LVH compared to non-hypertrophic patients (9.7 (3.3-32) ng/mg vs. 3.9 (2.4-25) ng/mg, $p=0.022$). When 8-OHdG/creatinine levels were compared according to gender we found a significant increase in women (12 (3.5-39) ng/mg vs. 4.3 (2.4-23) ng/mg, $p=0.006$). In addition, when urinary 8-OHdG/creatinine was compared according to obesity (BMI>30 kg/m²), diabetes and metabolic syndrome, no significant differences were found (5.7 (2.8-31) ng/mg vs. 6.4 (2.8-31) ng/mg, $p=0.973$, 5.4 (2.4-39) ng/mg vs. 6.4 (2.8-30) ng/mg, $p=0.996$ and 4.1 (2.6-24) ng/mg vs. 5.0 (2.8-23) ng/mg, $p=0.749$, respectively). Nevertheless, we found a significant increase in this biomarker of DNA damage in smokers (21 (3.6-48) ng/mg vs. 5.3 (2.7-28) ng/mg, $p=0.032$) (Figure 1).

Log-transformed urinary 8-OHdG/creatinine concentrations correlated with age ($r=0.351$, $p<0.0001$) and left ventricular mass index ($r=0.214$, $p<0.01$), but its levels

were not significantly correlated with systolic blood pressure, BMI, waist circumference, total cholesterol and HDL cholesterol ($r=0.133$, $p=0.107$, $r=0.130$, $p=0.118$, $r=-0.011$, $p=0.900$, $r=-0.100$, $p=0.278$ and $r=0.162$, $p=0.080$, respectively). Furthermore, urinary levels of this oxidative stress marker were also correlated with the plasma concentration of TNF-alpha ($r=0.66$, $p<0.0001$), its soluble receptors, sTNF-R1 and sTNF-R2 ($r=0.32$, $p<0.0001$; $r=0.36$, $p<0.0001$, respectively), and IL-6 ($r=0.20$, $p<0.05$). When we divided the levels of inflammatory mediators in quartiles and compared the concentration of 8-OHdG/creatinine, we found significant differences ($p<0.0001$) (Figure 2).

Finally, a multivariate linear regression analysis was used to test the independent predictive power of age, gender, known HT duration, Vp, LVH, cardiovascular risk factors (systolic blood pressure, BMI, total cholesterol, smoking and diabetes mellitus), and inflammation mediators (TNF-alpha, sTNF-R1 sTNF-R2 and IL-6), on urinary log-transformed 8-OHdG/creatinine. The best model included gender ($p=0.016$), smoking ($p=0.029$) and log transformed TNF-alpha ($p<0.0001$) as independent factors, accounting for an r^2 of 0.56 ($p<0.0001$) (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

In the present study we evaluated the influence of cardiovascular risk factors, and inflammation status on the levels of urinary 8-OHdG in a representative group of the hypertensive population. Hypertensive patients with LVH showed higher concentrations of this marker of oxidative DNA damage and we obtained a significant correlation between 8-OHdG and left ventricular mass index. Our hypertensive patients showed no significant differences in the urinary levels of this marker according to obesity and diabetes. However, smoking significantly increases urinary 8-OHdG levels.

In addition, only smoking, gender and TNF-alpha plasma levels were independent predictors of urinary 8-OHdG.

Some studies have shown that biomarkers of systemic oxidative stress are elevated in human hypertension³. In addition, it has been reported that among the main cardiovascular risk factors, hypertension is the strongest determinant of oxidative stress in a high risk cardiovascular population¹⁶. However, reports on the relationship between blood pressure and oxidative stress in essential hypertension are contradictory. Some findings show an association between blood pressure values and oxidative stress-related parameters²³, while other authors have shown an absence of correlation between these variables³. Our results indicate that blood pressure values are not correlated with urinary 8-OHdG in hypertensive patients undergoing medical treatment. These results may indicate that factors other than blood pressure values alone, inherent to the hypertensive status, may be contributing to the levels of this urinary marker of oxidative stress.

Although obesity and diabetes are highly associated with systemic oxidative stress¹, it has been reported that the impact of the different cardiovascular risk factors, such as low levels of high-density lipoprotein, triglycerides, abdominal obesity or fasting glucose, on 8-OHdG genomic and mitochondrial, is minimal in patients with essential HT¹⁵. Urinary 8-OHdG is considered a good marker for monitoring oxidative stress changes in hypertensive patients¹⁴. However, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have evaluated the influence of cardiovascular risk factors on the levels of this marker in patients with essential HT. Our results are in concordance with the analysis previously performed on 8-OHdG genomic and mitochondrial¹⁵. We show that the levels of this urinary marker are not associated with obesity, diabetes, and cholesterol levels in essential HT. Remarkably, we found higher levels of urinary 8-OHdG in smokers than in non-smokers, and smoking was independent predictor of

urinary 8-OHdG concentrations in these patients. These results are consistent with those previously reported in healthy people and in lung cancer patients^{24, 25}, this shows the deleterious action of tobacco in HT. While the association between chronic smoking and cardiovascular disease is well-established, the underlying mechanisms are not fully understood. Nevertheless, it is known that smoking exposure can increase systemic oxidative stress, alter nitric oxide bioavailability, cause endothelial dysfunction, and influence the levels of risk factors such as blood pressure²⁶⁻²⁹. We also observed that the value of urinary 8-OHdG between females and males is significantly different, in accordance with previously reported data².

LVH is the main mechanism of compensation for hemodynamic overload in HT and its presence adversely affects the prognosis of patients with arterial HT. Although many basic experimental studies strongly support a key role of oxidative stress in the pathophysiology of cardiac hypertrophic remodeling and dysfunction^{11, 12}, clinical data testing these findings remain scant. In the present study, we show for the first time, higher concentrations of urinary 8-OHdG in hypertensive patients with LVH compared to non-hypertrophic subjects, and we obtained a significant correlation between this marker of oxidative DNA damage and left ventricular mass index. Therefore in our patients the presence of LVH is associated with increased oxidative stress even in hypertensive subjects undergoing medical treatment. Nevertheless LVH was not an independent factor of 8-OHdG urinary levels.

In a previous report, our group showed that the levels of different cytokines were increased in hypertensive patients with LVH³⁰. On the other hand, several lines of evidences support a role for TNF-alpha, its soluble receptors and IL-6 as predictors of cardiovascular events^{31, 32}. In the present study we obtained a good correlation between 8-OHdG and inflammatory markers, and we found that TNF-alpha plasma levels were

independent predictors of urinary 8-OHdG. IL-6 was not. There is a complex interaction between cytokine-mediated inflammation and oxidative stress and several studies have shown the close relationship between circulating levels of inflammatory cytokines and several markers of oxidative stress in hypertensive patients^{9, 10, 33}. Some authors have suggested that cytokines not only induce the production of ROS, but the synthesis of cytokines may be induced by ROS³⁴⁻³⁶. The increase in cardiomyocyte stretching is the main factor inducing hypertrophic growth, but circulating substances, such as oxidative stress products or cytokines, released locally by the myocardial cells, also induce hypertrophy³⁷. Thus, it seems that there is no isolated signaling cascade for each stimulus or response, but rather that multiple signaling molecules occur and can form a network of cascades with numerous elements, facilitating their crossing-over. Here, for first time we have shown a strongly correlation between 8-OHdG and TNF-alpha, which has been shown to be index of patients prognosis. These markers may indicate an increase in cardiovascular risk in hypertensive patients and this may have therapeutic consequences since blood pressure may not be the only target. Angiotensin II receptor blockers have been shown to possess benefits in addition to their ability to lower blood pressure, including anti-inflammatory and antioxidative properties^{38, 39}. In addition, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and beta blockers have been shown to decrease levels of some oxidative stress-related parameters³⁹. However, this study confirms that a high degree of oxidative damage persists in hypertensive patients with LVH even during standard therapy and this activation can be detected in urine. In this sense, we think that 8-OHdG may give additional information about the level of risk and could be used to optimize medical treatment further than blood pressure control alone.

A potential limitation is that although echocardiography-standardized techniques have been shown to be a more specific tool for detecting LVH than electrocardiographic measurements⁴⁰, the variability of this technique is higher than the variability reported for magnetic resonance imaging. However, in the present study a single, blinded, specialized cardiologist performed the echocardiographic analyses used to measure left ventricular mass to minimize variability.

In conclusion, urinary levels of 8-OHdG are increased in our hypertensive patients with LVH under medical treatment. Nevertheless LVH was not an independent factor of 8-OHdG. The presence of cardiovascular risk factors, such as obesity, diabetes and hypercholesterolemia on top of HT, does not alter the concentrations of this oxidative stress marker, only smoking increasing its levels. In addition, TNF-alpha is an independent factor of 8-OHdG. **These data suggest that this urinary marker gives specific additional information, further than blood pressure control alone, when evaluating hypertensive patients.**

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure

None declared

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LEGENDS

Figure 1. Urinary 8-OHdG levels in patients with essential hypertension according to the presence of left ventricular hypertrophy (A), obesity (B), diabetes mellitus (C), and smoking (D). 8-OHdG: 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine, LVH: left ventricular hypertrophy.

Figure 2. Levels of inflammatory mediators in quartiles, TNF-alpha (A), sTNF-R1 (B) and sTNF-R2 (C), to compare the concentration of 8-OHdG/creatinine. 8-OHdG: 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine, sTNF-R1: soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1, sTNF-R2: soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2; TNF: tumor necrosis factor.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics and echocardiographic parameters of hypertensive patients.

Variable	n=149
Age (years)	61 ± 14
Gender (male %)	55
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	136 ± 15
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	80 ± 9
Heart rate (bpm)	70 ± 11
Known HT duration (months)	119 ± 101
GFR (mL/min/1.73m ²)	94 ± 33
Glucose (mg/dL)	107 ± 25
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	204 ± 33
HDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	52 ± 14
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	30 ± 4
Obesity (%)	43
Diabetes mellitus (%)	16
Current Smokers (%)	15
LVH (%)	46
Troponin T levels (ng/mL)	0.01 ± 0.002
TNF-alpha (pg/mL)	4.2 (2.3-7.6)
sTNF-R1 (pg/mL)	382 (291-516)

sTNF-R2 (pg/mL)	851 (606-1296)
IL-6 (pg/mL)	1.86 (1.17-2.93)
Echocardiographic parameters	
EF (%)	60 ± 5
E/A	0.9 ± 0.2
Vp (cm/s)	51 ± 14
DT (ms)	201 ± 35
IVRT (ms)	93 ± 8
LVMI (g/m ^{2.7})	51 ± 18

Clinical variables are expressed as the mean value ± SD or median (interquartile range)

or percentage of subjects. DT = deceleration time; E/A = early (E) mitral inflow peak/atrial (A) filling peak ratio; EF = ejection fraction; GFR = glomerular filtration rate; HT = hypertension; HDL = high density lipoprotein; IL-6 = interleukin-6; IVRT = isovolumetric relaxation time; LVH = left ventricular hypertrophy; LVMI = left ventricular mass indexed by height^{2.7}; sTNF-R1 = soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1, sTNF-R2 = soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2; TNF = tumor necrosis factor; Vp = mitral flow propagation velocity.

Table 2. Multivariate linear regression results for detecting independent factors on log-transformed urinary 8-OHdG/creatinine in hypertensive patients

	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	S.E.	p Value	B	S.E.	p Value
Age	0.014	0.005	0.003	0.008	0.005	0.081
Gender	-0.334	0.115	0.005	-0.251	0.102	0.016
Systolic blood pressure	-0.007	0.004	0.192	-0.005	0.003	0.124
Known HT duration	0.000	0.000	0.816	0.000	0.000	0.296
Total cholesterol	-0.002	0.002	0.216	-0.002	0.001	0.081
Body mass index	-0.001	0.011	0.970	-0.003	0.011	0.767
Diabetes mellitus	-0.068	0.136	0.618	-0.060	0.119	0.618
Current smoking	0.283	0.117	0.017	0.222	0.100	0.029
LVH	0.014	0.129	0.917	0.013	0.112	0.317
Vp	0.004	0.005	0.409	0.002	0.004	0.582
log TNF-alpha	-	-	-	0.465	0.084	0.0001
log sTNF-R1	-	-	-	-0.136	0.297	0.648
log sTNF-R2	-	-	-	0.139	0.244	0.572
log IL-6	-	-	-	0.160	0.154	0.301

Model 1 of regression analysis was associated with an $r^2=0.32$ ($p=0.002$) and Model 2 was associated with an $r^2=0.56$ ($p<0.0001$). HT = hypertension; LVH = left ventricular hypertrophy; log IL-6 = log-transformed interleukin-6; log sTNF-R1 = log-transformed soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1, log sTNF-R2 = log-transformed soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2; log TNF = log-transformed tumor necrosis factor; Vp = mitral flow propagation velocity.

FIGURE 1

